

A comprehensive national scale human mobility data asset for Australia

ARDC AUSTRALIAN DATA PARTNERSHIPS PROGRAM
PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	DP702
PROJECT START AND END DATES	Jan 2021 - Dec 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	CSIRO
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	QUT University of Melbourne AURIN
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Kamran Najeebullah (was Jessica Liebig)

1.1 Background

The Mobility Australia project addressed the critical need for comprehensive human mobility data to understand and manage the spread of infectious diseases, particularly highlighted during the COVID-19 pandemic. Recognizing limitations and constrained accessibility of existing datasets, the project focused on leveraging publicly available datasets related to human mobility, such as population census, public transport patronage, and road network usage.

The initiative aimed to consolidate diverse mobility datasets from various sources into a standardized, accessible format. By merging these datasets, the project significantly enhanced the quality and coverage of existing data, addressing the challenge of disparate data collection across multiple organizations, agencies and departments.

Beyond its primary focus on infectious disease modelling, there is a broader utility of this dataset in the fields such as policy and administration, transport, logistics and supply chains, criminology, emergency, disaster and environmental management, and pollution and contamination management. The data has a massive potential in significantly contributing to advancing research and understanding of human mobility patterns as well as benefitting various scientific disciplines and sectors reliant on such data.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

In line with the identified research purpose and target research community described above, the project identified 16 state and national level datasets on human mobility flow counts, mode of transportation, and behaviour in response to social/mobility restrictions enforced in response to COVID-19 pandemic. Understanding the importance and significance of human mobility patterns during the pandemic induced social restrictions, opposed to the initial plan of limiting the focus of the project to pre-pandemic data (i.e., 2019), the scope of the project was calibrated to include the years impacted by the pandemic i.e., 2020-2022 (depending on availability of data from the original source).

The selected datasets were spatially and temporally standardised into a single comprehensive data silo to improve data quality and facilitate data analytics. Each dataset posed a unique challenge. Algorithms were tailored to suite every individual dataset considering their differences while at the same time their similarities were leveraged to lower the complexity of the solution. Spatially, the data was aggregated on Statistical Area Level 2 (SA2) level for all states except Tasmania. Temporal dimensions vary depending on data availability. The aggregations applied are day-of-week by calendar month and day-of-week by calendar year where day of week is Monday to Sunday. For datasets that don't provide data for days of week independently a weekday/weekend aggregation is applied. The spatial and temporal resolution of the data was set through consultation with project partners and stakeholders and considering the computational constraints with respect to project timeline. Data from various sources including, traffic volumes, population census and public transport patronage are combined to improve coverage by achieving a better representative sample of the population mobility.

The final data asset will be hosted by AURIN and made accessible through an API, ensuring discoverability and usability. Standardisation of the spatial resolution to statistical area levels significantly improves the usability, making the datasets that were largely of interest to specialised research community accessible to a more general audience, including non-scientific.

The Python code written to curate, process and integrate the data will be made publicly accessible, allowing for reproduction of the data. Raw data acquired from the public data sources will also be made available. This is to ensure the code base remains relevant in the event if changes were made effecting the availability or format of the public data sources.

Governance and management of the final dataset will be performed through AURIN's data platform. AURIN will keep track of the citation, acknowledgements and number of downloads of the data. The project team plan to submit at least two publications arising from the project, one purely dedicated to the availability, accessibility, and discoverability of the data resource. A citation record of the publications will also be maintained for governance purposes.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	COMPLETION DATE
Analysis of individual datasets	The analysis of over 24 different data sets was performed. Multiple instances of the datasets covering multiple years were analysed with datasets often changing over time in format and resolution.	31/11/2021
Report describing the information contained in the various datasets	A report on the analysis of the individual data sets have previously been provided.	23/12/2021
Literature review of OD matrices	The relevant literature has been reviewed and suitable techniques have been identified.	30/11/2021
Determine methodologies for creating OD matrices	Methodologies to create OD matrices by combining existing and new techniques have been defined and is included in the meta data document.	25/02/2022
Cleaning of datasets	The select datasets were pre-processed to address data anomalies like missing or incorrect data.	31/07/2022
Workshop for stakeholders	The project team has decided that at this stage a workshop for stakeholders is not useful. We are planning to run one workshop at the end of the project to introduce stakeholders to the API.	31/12/2023

Processing individual datasets	The selected datasets have been processed as well as spatially and temporally standardised	31/12/2023
Merging of OD matrices	The data has been aggregated by different mode of transport i.e., public, or private transportation. The merging can be performed by taking the sum over unique OD pairs. We are in discussions with AURIN on whether to leave the choice to the user on merging that datasets together or provide a single data source for simplicity.	31/12/2023
Report of outcomes	Report of outcomes have been maintained as a live document over the course of the project providing the detailed description of how each data source is processed and transformed including all the limitations and assumptions. The report will be further refined. (https://www.overleaf.com/read/tyxyhbimcpwt)	31/12/2023
Planning of project continuity	The Python code written to curate, process and integrate the data will be made publicly accessible, allowing for reproduction of the data. Raw data acquired from the public data sources will also be made available. This is to ensure the code base remains relevant in the event if changes were made effecting the availability or format of the public data sources.	31/01/2023
Workshop for stakeholders	The project team has decided that at this stage a workshop for stakeholders is not useful. We are planning to run one workshop at the end of the project to introduce stakeholders to the API.	31/12/2023
Implementation of database architecture for OD retrieval	The OD retrieval is based on AURIN's well tested architecture that is being widely used for other similar data solutions.	31/01/2023

Development of API	Given the simplicity of the output data structure (and OD matrix). AURIN has decided (and with our agreement) that a sophisticated API was not required, rather a simple data ingestion method would be used that would allow data updates through OD file uploads.	31/12/2023
Incorporation of visualisation tool for data asset	The team at AURIN has developed a project plan for phase 3 to ensure the tasks for this phase stay on track.	31/12/2023
API documentation for end users	The team at AURIN has developed a project plan for phase 3 to ensure the tasks for this phase stay on track. The documentation will be showcased in the introductory workshop for user training purposes.	31/12/2023
Development and testing of data processing and curation pipelines	Provided the unreliable nature of the opensource data that regularly undergo unpredictable changes to the data and storage structure, file formats and download procedures. The project team has reached a conclusion that a human supervised pre-processing step maybe required for any future reproduction of the database. Once the data & storage structure and file formatting requirements are met, the provided data processing and curation pipeline would be able to reproduce the future iterations of the database.	n/a
Workshop to introduce API to stakeholders	We plan to open this workshop to community to obtain diverse feedback from a wider user base. All project partners (CSIRO, UoM, QUT and AURIN) will collaboratively work on arranging a virtual workshop to present on going work on data access storage and visualization. The steering committee and AURIN leadership has generously shared their expertise and experience from the users' perspective. CSIRO has started promoting the data internally and externally, with the project showcased at the Human Health	31/12/2023 These activities, except for the stakeholder workshop, has been undertaken. The stakeholder workshop is delayed until the

	<p>Showcase and forums for early and mid-career researchers. CSIRO also plan to showcase this work at the upcoming Epidemics 9 conference in Bologna, Italy. AURIN is as well as University of Melbourne are also interested in showcasing this work one the data become publicly available.</p>	<p>publication of related manuscript.</p>
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2.2 Project outputs

- 1- A comprehensive, spatially, and temporally standardised human mobility dataset, covering all states of Australia except Tasmania and an associated API to access and visualise the data (AURIN is also planning on providing some basic analyses).
- 2- A meta data report containing the details on how each individual dataset was transformed, including the methodology, assumptions, and limitations.
- 3- The raw data acquired from various sources and the Python code base used to transform the data.
- 4- At least two journal articles (currently in writing) introducing the data and the methodology.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
CSIRO Human Health Showcase	Mobility Australia project was introduced to the Human Health researchers' cohort, including experts in epidemiology, and public health.	300	May 6-8, 2023
CSIRO Health and Biosecurity All Hands	The project was introduced to a larger group of researchers in human health, eHealth, and biosecurity programs of the Health and Biosecurity units including their associates at	900	September 4, 2023

	various universities and research institutes across Australia.		
Epidemics 9	The project will soon be introduced in the 9th International Conference on Infectious Disease Dynamics in Bologna, Italy with experts in epidemiology and public health joining from around the world.	700	November 28 – December 1, 2023
Stakeholder workshop	All project partners (CSIRO, UoM, QUT and AURIN) are working collaboratively on arranging a virtual workshop to showcase the project and introduce the data access storage and visualization components.	n/a	Before the end of the year or potentially early next year to make it more accessible.

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

AURIN maintains a preservation policy that guarantees sustained accessibility to both data and its associated metadata. This policy forms the foundation for continuous operation, maintenance, and enhancement of the data asset. Moreover, the raw data sourced from various sources and the Python code will be preserved beyond the project's conclusion, undergoing review every five years. The University of Melbourne presently manages a long-term storage plan for the raw data, while the code resides in a Bitbucket repository. AURIN plans to make both the raw data and code publicly visible alongside the processed data.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	AURIN assigns an internal PID when ingested. AURIN are also in the process of incorporating DOI creation into the ingestion process and when completed will create a DOI for Mobility Australia data if required.
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	Yes, the dataset abstract on the data download page has a link to meta data file
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	As per AURIN policy, the AURIN data catalogue is synchronised with RDA.
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (Recommended , if they exist)	The AURIN data provider platform is equipped with this functionality.
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	Each data output has an internal PID in addition to other persistent identifiers AURIN API ID and a unique landing page URL.
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	Yes, data outputs are provided under creative commons license the exact version of the license is dictated by the license of the data used to generate the output.
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	All data outputs are available through the AURIN data provider platform.
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed)	Yes, AURIN Data Provider (ADP). The ADP is behind authentication wall, however all AAF listed organisations have access and account creation is open to all upon request.
9	If the data outputs are not openly	Yes, where someone is not from an AAF listed

	available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met	organisation there are links to create an account.
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	AURIN is in the process of implementing DOI based persistent identifiers for their entire data catalogue. Between now and the time a DOI is implemented the URL should be persistent, serving as an interim ID that is available to all even if data is restricted.
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data	Yes, open to AAF organisations and account request process open to all others.
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages	AURIN has preservation policy that ensures metadata will be made available even if data is unavailable.
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist)	Yes, data is served over Open Geospatial Consortium Web Feature Services enabling multiple download options.
14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist)	Yes, data is checked against ISO19115 metadata when ingested into AURIN.
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (Recommended , preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist)	Data are mapped to Fields of Research codes when submitted to AURIN however AURIN is currently reviewing this space.
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCID, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs)	Reviewed and implemented by AURIN where appropriate.
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0)	Yes, CC BY 4.0

18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) refers to	Yes, Licence is listed and hyperlinked on the landing page
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier refers to	Yes, there is attribution statement on the landing page
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data (Recommended)	A metadata document is provided with the Mobility Australia dataset, which provides information on data origin, assumptions, and transformation methods to ensure provenance and enable reproducibility and reuse.
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice (Recommended)	A metadata document is provided with the Mobility Australia dataset, which provides information on data origin, assumptions, and transformation methods to ensure provenance and enable reproducibility and reuse.

5 PROJECT IMPACT

The ARDC and the Government wish to demonstrate the impact on researchers, industry and the general public of the NCRIS investment.

5.1 Communications and Engagement

These activities have been reported above in the outreach and training activities section. In addition, for the benefit of wider audience, CSIRO, AURIN, UoM and QUT will all advertise the project through their media teams once it is publicly available. This includes creation of home page for the project to make the data, training materials, code and raw data visible and accessible, social media posts and media releases.

At least two manuscripts are currently in writing and will be submit to suitable journals at completion.

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	A monitoring framework has been established (see below).
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	The project benefitted from the expertise, experience and knowledge of the stakeholders, steering committee members and partners belonging to a wide array of research domain and areas.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	AURIN with their vast experience and track-record of working with user-facing data solutions served the project as the research translations specialist.
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	<p>AURIN through their data management system will monitor access to the data and can provide indication of usage in the form of API hits.</p> <p>AURIN also monitors all publications where AURIN is cited or acknowledged.</p>

Monitoring Framework

The outcomes and impacts of the proposed data asset will be monitored and evaluated on a regular basis. We have identified two lists of indicators (taken from the OECD’s Reference Framework for Assessing the Scientific and Socio-Economic Impact of Research Infrastructure) that are relevant for the construction and the operational phases of the data asset.

Indicators for the construction phase:

- Number of publications in high-impact factor journals
- Knowledge sharing
- Data sharing

Indicators for the operational phase:

- Number of citations

- Number of publications in high-impact factor journals
- Number of scientific users
- Public visibility of the data asset
- Knowledge sharing
- Data sharing

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

Managing diverse, disparate, and sometimes incomplete data sources poses significant challenges. The project team successfully devised a standardized approach applied uniformly to streamline each data source into a probabilistic network flow formation. This approach facilitated algorithm and code reusability and allowed time for refining methodologies.

Collaboration with QUT and the University of Melbourne provided access to extensive programming and research resources, proving invaluable as team members transitioned to other opportunities throughout the project's three-year duration. Partnership with AURIN proved advantageous, leveraging their extensive experience in client-facing data solutions.

Engaging a diverse (in terms of research expertise) stakeholder and steering committee ensured confidence in our outcomes, free from bias toward any specific research domain perspective. This diversity empowered the team to progress confidently.